

SECTIONALLY PSEUDOCOMPLEMENTED RESIDUAL LATTICE

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Abstract : At first, we recall the basic concept, By a residual lattice is meant an algebra $L = (L, \vee, \wedge, *, \circ, 0, 1)$ such that

(i) $L = (L, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ is a bounded lattice,

(ii) $L = (L, *, 1)$ is a commutative monoid,

(iii) it satisfies the so-called adjointness property: $(x \vee y) * z = y$ if and only if $y \leq z \leq x \circ y$

Let us note [7] that $x \vee y$ is the greatest element of the set $(x \vee y) * z = y$

Moreover, if we consider $x * y = x \wedge y$, then $x \circ y$ is the relative pseudo-complement of x with respect to y , i. e., for $* = \wedge$ residuated lattices are just relatively pseudo-complemented lattices. The identities characterizing sectionally pseudo-complemented lattices are presented in [3] i.e. the class of these lattices is a variety in the signature $\{\vee, \wedge, \circ, 1\}$. We are going to apply a similar approach for the adjointness property:

Key words: Residuated lattice, non Distributive, Residuated Abelian, commutative monoid:

1. Introduction

Residuated lattices were introduced by Ward and Dilworth [5] and studied by several authors. Two monographs contain a compendium on residuated lattices. They are that by Blyth and Janowitz [1] (where it is renamed as a residuated Abelian semi-group with a unit) and the book by R. Belohavek [7]. In this short note we will compare a certain modification of a residuated lattice with already introduced [2], [3]. At first, we recall the basic concept:

Definition 1. A lattice $L = (L, \vee, \wedge, 1)$ with the greatest element 1 is sectionally pseudo-complemented if each interval $[y, 1]$ is a pseudo-complemented lattice.

From now on, denote by $x \vee y$ the pseudo-complement of $x \vee y$ in the interval $[y, 1]$.

Naturally, $x \vee y \in [y, 1]$ thus $L = (L; \vee, \wedge, 1)$ is sectionally pseudo-complemented if and only if " \circ " is an (everywhere defined) operation on L .

Definition 2. An algebra $L = (L; \vee, \wedge, *, \circ, 1)$ is called a sectionally residuated lattice if

(i) $L = (L, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ is a lattice with the greatest element 1;

(ii) $L = (L, *, 1)$ is a commutative monoid ;

(iii) it satisfies the sectional adjointness property: $(x \vee y) * z = y$ if and only if $y \leq z \leq x \circ y$

Lemma 1.1 Let $L = (L; \vee, \wedge, *, \circ, 1)$ be a sectionally residuated lattice. Then $x * y$ is the greatest element of the set $\{z; (x \vee y) * z = y\}$

This immediately yields the following facts:

$$(x \vee y) * (x \circ y) = y, \quad (1)$$

$$(x \vee y) * y = y, \quad (2)$$

$$y \leq x \circ y, \quad (3)$$

Lemma 1.2 Let $L = (L; \vee, \wedge, *, \circ, 1)$ be a sectionally residuated lattice. Then $x \leq y$, if and only if $x \circ y = 1$

Proof: Suppose $x \leq y$, Then $x \vee y = y$, and by Lemma 1.1, $x \circ y$ is the greatest element of the set $\{z; y * z = y\}$ By Definition 2, $y * 1 = 1$ thus $x \circ y = 1$. Conversely,

Suppose $x \circ y = 1$. Then, by [1], we have $y = (x \vee y) * (x \circ y) = (x \vee y) * 1 = x \vee y$

whence $x \leq y$

Lemma 1.3 In a sectionally residuated lattice, the following identities are satisfied:

and $1 \circ x = x$

Proof: The first three identities follow directly by Lemma 1.2. Further, by Lemma 1.1,

$1 \circ x$ is the greatest element of the set $\{z; 1 * z = x\} = \{x\}$ thus $1 \circ x = x$

Lemma 1.4 In a sectionally residuated lattice, $a * b = a$ if and only if $a = b$

Proof: Putting $x = y = a$ and $z = b$ in the sectional adjointness property, the assumption $a * b = a$ yields $(a \vee a) * b$ iff $a \leq b \leq a \circ a = 1$ thus $a \leq b$

Conversely, $a \leq b$ implies by Lemma 3 $a \leq b \leq 1 = a \circ a$ and, by sectional adjointness, $a * b = (a \vee a) * b = a$

Applying Lemma 1.2 and Lemma 1.4, we get

Corollary 1.5 In a sectionally residuated lattice,

(a) $x * y = x$ if and only if $x \circ y = 1$;

(b) $x * x = x$

Lemma 1.6 In a sectionally residuated lattice, $x \wedge y \leq x * y$.

Proof: By [3] we have $x \wedge y \leq x \circ (x \wedge y)$.

Applying sectional adjointness, we infer $x * (x \wedge y) = (x \vee (x \wedge y)) * (x \wedge y)$ and, analogously, $y * (x \wedge y) = x \wedge y$. Hence, by Corollary 1.5 (b),

$$\begin{aligned} x * y * (x \wedge y) &= x * (x \wedge y) * y * (x \wedge y) \\ &= (x \wedge y) * (x \wedge y) = x \wedge x \end{aligned}$$

and by Lemma 1.4, $x \wedge y \leq x * y$.

Theorem 1.7 Let $L = (L; \vee, \wedge, *, \circ, 1)$ be a sectionally residuated lattice. Then it is a sectionally pseudo-complemented lattice.

Proof: Replacing y by $x \wedge y$ in the sectional adjointness property, we obtain $x * z = x \wedge y$ iff $x \wedge y \leq z \leq x \circ (x \wedge y)$.

However, $x \circ (x \wedge y)$ is the greatest element of the set $\{t; (x \vee (x \wedge y)) * t = x \wedge y\} = \{t; x * t = x \wedge y\}$.

By Lemma 1.4, $x \wedge t \leq x * t = x \wedge y$, thus the greatest t of this property satisfies $t \geq y$.

Thus $y \leq x \circ (x \wedge y)$, i.e., $x \wedge y \leq y \leq x \circ (x \wedge y)$ and by the sectional adjointness, $x * y = (x \wedge (x \vee y)) * y = x \wedge y$.

Hence, $x \circ y$ is the pseudo-complement of $x \vee y$ in the interval $[y, 1]$

2. Conclusion

It is well known that every relatively pseudo-complemented lattice is distributive.

An extension of relative pseudo-complementation for the non-distributive case was already involved in [3], [4]:

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